

Comparative Relationship between Traditional Beliefs and Forest Resource Management among Stakeholders in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria

Usang, Nkanu Onnoghen¹

usangonnoghen@gmail.com,

+2348171953333

Rose, Usang Onnoghen¹

Roseosang012@gmail.com,

+2347039097094

Unimtiang, Unimke Sylvanus²

unimkefelaa@gmail.com,

+2347034477327

Ogbaji Dominic Ipuole³

Dominicogbaji2@gmail.com,

+2348035280651

Nwagbara, Moses O.³

Moses.nwagbara@mouau.edu.ng, momwagbara@yahoo.com

¹Department of Environmental Education, Faculty of Arts and Social Science Education, University of Calabar

²Department of Social Science Education, Faculty of Arts and Social Science Education, University of Calabar

³Department of Water Resources Management and Agrometeorology, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to examine comparative relationship between traditional beliefs and forest resource management among stakeholders in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was raised. Correlational research design was adopted. The estimated projected population for the study is 108,140 adult respondents. Stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting five communities (wards) used for the study. Systematic random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 300 respondents. A self-developed questionnaire “Traditional Belief and Forest Resource Management (TBFRM)” was used to obtain data. The research instruments were given for scrutiny to three experts in research and statistics. The items were subjected to content validity and reliability by the specialists. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha technique. The coefficient (r) of the instrument was high at 0.75-0.78. Data were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistical tool for hypotheses testing. The findings obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in the study area. Based on the findings obtained in the study, the researcher made the following recommendations Agricultural extension workers and Environmental Educators should continue to encourage farmer to engage in conservation method in order to promote forest resources conservation in the study area.

Keywords: traditional beliefs, forest, resources, conservation, Yakurr Local Government Area

Introduction

The issue of forest resource conservation has in recent times called for global discourse and debate in many countries of the world. Forest resource conservation is the judicious use of forest resources in a way that maintains the biodiversity, productivity, regeneration capacity and their potential to fulfil the present and future generation. Forest is gift of nature and it contains all sorts of important natural resources. The importance of forest goes beyond the provision of physical needs of human; to exert tremendous impacts on our environment. The role of forest resource in the environment and every living thing that depends on it directly or indirectly is indeed unique.

Forest forms an integral part of the biosphere, essential to the stabilization of global climate and the management of water and land resources. They are home to countless plants and animals that are vital elements of our life support system. In spite of its importance, forest resources are plagued by several problems when viewed from different perspectives. Many forests land has difficulties of reproducing and some cannot give maximum benefit to man. Much of our forest resources have been lost through deforestation, lack of adequate sensitization of community members regarding forest resource conservation, logging, abuse of indigenous law and regulation, unsustainable farming methods, uncontrolled bush burning amongst others. The consequences of these malpractice include loss of biodiversity, soil infertility, land degradation and exposure to agent of erosion (FAO,2015).

Conservation of natural resources is the wise use of the earth's resources by humanity. It is the management of valuable natural resources such as timber, fish, topsoil, pastureland, and minerals, forests, wildlife, parkland, wilderness and watershed areas. According to (Appiah-Opoku, 2017), to regulate interactions with their natural environment, the role of traditional beliefs in the conservation of a large number of elements of local biodiversity, regardless of their use value, dates back to creation. Berkes, (2010) confirm that traditional conservation ethics are capable of protecting biodiversity species in particular and the environment in general as long as the local communities have a stake in it.

Similarly, Eneji, Gubo, Jian, Oden and Okpiliya (2009b) have pointed out that the existence of traditional beliefs/taboo does not guarantee sustainable harvest of natural resources. Traditional African religion (ATR) and cultural practices as done in most part of African communities are environmentally friendly and sustainable, thus contributing so much to natural resources sustainability and conservation. In Africa and indeed Nigeria, the traditional belief system holds the ascription of supernatural powers to objects called gods and goddesses. The major tenet of African traditional religion and belief system lies in the belief that the abode of the gods and goddesses is located on rock, streams, pond, tress, land or anywhere they so desire to live within the community. The gods choose their followers through the rites of initiation with a core messenger who is the mouth piece of the gods living among human beings. The gods or goddess communicate its will to the people through the juju priest or chief priest.

The belief system is that the gods protect the community members from harm, famine, impotence, drought, epidemics and war among others. The gods avenge their anger on whoever omits or commits any flaw for which their presence forbids; hence, the cultural system holds to a very high esteem all the precepts of the laws of the gods (Shastri, etal, 2012). Tiwari (2018) also maintained that the role of traditional beliefs in the protection of natural resources is reflected in a variety of practices including sacred groves and sacred landscapes. For example, in India, particular patches of forests are designated as sacred groves under customary law and are protected from any product extraction by the community. Such forests are very rich in biological diversity and harbor many endangered plant species including rare herbs and medicinal plants.

A study conducted by Sam (2018) examined the influence of African traditional religion and practices on sustainable conservation of natural resources in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Two null hypotheses were formulated to direct the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.5level of significance. The literature reviewed was based on the sub variable of the study. The survey research design was adopted for the study. the choice of this design was to enable the researcher examine the phenomena under investigation as it exists presently in the study area. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to select six autonomous communities that have played significant role in conversation or the natural resources available in the environment. To select the 400 respondents used for the study stratified random sampling techniques was used. The questionnaire was the instrument used to obtain data for the data. The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability test. The result of the test showed the calculated value range of .85 to .97 which implies that, the instrument is reliable enough to measure what is was purported to measure. Data obtained for this study was tested using person product moment correlation (r) statistical analysis. The result obtained from data analysis revealed that, there is a significant relationship between totemism practice, evil forest practice and sustainable conservation of natural resources in the study area. Based on the result from the findings, conclusion and recommendation were made. One of the recommendations is that environmental conservation issues should form an integral part of teaching in various churches and mosque in the country to help reinforce positive attitude among their members and change negative one.

In a study Henshey (2011) posited that in traditional African societies like Nigeria, Ghana, and many others, many people believed that rocks, trees, streams, ponds and forests were the manifestation of the power of the Supreme Being. He saw these things as ideal places to meet their supreme being or the gods. In almost every traditional African setting or community, each community has what they revere or hold sacred either as the presence of their gods or their goddesses, or there is a very important symbolic reason attached to such objects in the course of their existence. In almost every community in Cross River, there is hardly any community that exists without a sacred groove, evil forest, sacred pond, evil stream, or forbidden forest. Where some part of the environment is delineated for the worship of the gods (Eneji et al., 2009).

There is an evil forest at Idomi and Mkpani in Yakurr, these evil forests are where bad people e.g., in the community are sent to go and die. If you are a witch or a wizard and have caused havoc in the community, or one dies in an accident such as auto crash or from a tree or palm tree, such corpse are taken to this forest. Some of these evil forests are the burial ground for the royals of the community. In Biase, there is also a burial ground for slaves, nobody wants to be associated with slavery, so the area remains a very thick forest since it is believed that the last slave buried there was before the stopping of slave trade in Nigeria. In Alifokpa in Yache, in Yala local government area, there is also a sacred grove where the remains of the ancestral fathers of the Alifokpa people were buried hundreds of years ago, no farming, felling of trees or harvesting of vegetables is done here. There is also a pond in Yache in Yala Local Government Area, which nobody goes near there, here crocodile, iguana and some wild sea animals are found here. If anybody strays to this pond, the person may be eaten by the wild beast, but the community believes that the person would be killed by the spirit. In Bateriko, some part of the forest is strictly reserve as the home of the gods, here no entrance is allowed into this forest, even when crops are cultivated close to the area, it does not give any good yield (Eneji, 2009). According to Sam and Usang (2018) traditional belief is seen as custom, traditions; culture held by indigenous people or local people and is passed down within a group or society from one generation to another. Non-Governmental Organization which at regulating and advises the urban and local Council and Commissioners on topics relating to forestry practices on forest land.

The literature reviewed reveals various relationships between traditional beliefs as the related to forest resource management. The literature presented various views and findings from different authors and researchers consulted in the study. It was observed that most literature available on the subject matter under investigation was outside the study area of this research work. Therefore, the findings of this study will provide both empirical and theoretical literature on the phenomena under study in the study area. From the review, it is noticeable that numerous studies are related to this present study. The review as also shown that most of the studies, even for those carried out in the present study area, have a different focus from the present study in of the independent and dependent variables, it is against this background that the present study will bridge the gap between traditional belief and forest resource conservation in Yakurr Local Government area of Cross River State.

The findings of this study will be of utmost importance to students, members of host communities, Ministry of Environment, forestry commission, non-governmental organizations, policy makers and researchers. To students of Environmental Education and other related disciplines it will be a source of acquiring relevant information and knowledge on the issues under investigation. To the host communities used for this study it shall be a source of acquiring knowledge that would improve their understanding on how their actions and activities contribute to the conservation of forests resources either negatively or positively. The Ministry of Environment will also benefit from the finding of this study as a source of acquiring more information on the relationship between community participation and forest resources conservation. Non-governmental organizations working on forest conservation can use the finding of this study as a working document for improving their various intervention activities and programs aimed at promoting sustainable forest management among forest communities.

The Forestry Commission will also use the result obtained from this study as a source of feedback for their various forest conservation intervention approaches and programs. Policy makers will also use the finding of this study as a source of baseline data for formulating new and more effective policies that would eliminate the various threats to effective forest conservation and management. Researchers intending to carry out a similar study on a broader scope or in other locations will see the finding of this study as a reference material for their various studies

Despite the relevance of forest resources to the maintenance of healthy environment, much harm has been done to the forest ecosystem. Unbridled logging, bush burning, overgrazing, hunting and mining among others, are common in the study area and these unsustainable environmental practices tend to endanger the existing forest resources in the area. The resultant effects of these unsustainable practices include climate change, global warming, drought, loss of biodiversity, loss of fertile land required for improved food product and so on. Efforts have been made by government to cushion these outcomes through the establishment of forest laws, introduction of nomadic education to improve individual knowledge of forest resource conservation, awareness creation through television programs, jingles, radio, conferences among others to control the unwarranted destruction of forest resources and its consequences has not yielded desired results. This unfortunate situation may be attributed to ignorance of rural dwellers about the importance of the sustainable use of forest resources for continued human survival. This implies that residents especially in the rural communities do not have the requisite knowledge, skills, information, and ideas to exploit forest resources sustainably. It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate the relationship between traditional belief and forest resource management in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Robert Lanza's Biocentric theory (1997); This theory was propounded by Robert Lanza in 1997. The theory holds that nature is sacred and as such should be revered or respected. This theory apart from emphasizing man's interdependence with nature further holds that the living and non-living things were created before man and therefore have their own right of existence

in spite of man. The emphasis is that man should live tenderly with nature in natural or symbiotic existence. African culture and most indigenous cultures the worlds over before the advent of colonization were actually given to the biocentric world-view value judgment about nature. In fact, not only were the Africans or native tribes' conscious of their interdependence with nature, the event went as far as ascribing life and supernatural power to nature. All these made it imperative to conserve nature.

The relevance of this theory to the present study is that, the bio-centric world-view promotes and lays the foundation for biodiversity conservation and management at various levels. This view is against wanton destruction and unsustainable exploitation of biodiversity and emphasize that man is not superior to nature but should live in natural or symbiotic relationship with it. Thus, considering the right of these natural resources to exist within the environment and their relevance to him justifies the view point of the theory. This theory is the basis for sustainable utilization and management of natural resources as well as sustainable development. Based on these, the forest resources conservation takes its root from the value judgment of this theory.

The main purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between traditional belief and forest resource conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between traditional belief and conservation of forest resources.

Methodology

The survey design was considered most suitable for the study. It allows the researcher to access the situation under investigation as it exists presently and which involves the collection of data accurately and objectively describe phenomena in the current time and the focus to ascertain facts. The study was carried out in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. Yakurr is one of the eighteen Local Government Areas of Cross River State. It has a landmass of about (2,771 km²). It is located between latitude 6° 16'26" North longitudes, 9°0'36"East. The area is bounded to the North by Obubra Local Government Area, to the south by Biase, to the west by Akankpa and to the East by Abi LGA (Wikipedia.com). The 2023 population projection for Yakurr is 864,200 persons (National Population Commission, 2023). The population of this study consisted of all adult residents in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The actual population includes farmers, hunters, students, traders, business men/women. The estimated projected population for the study is about 108,140 persons (National Population Commission, 2022).

Stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the communities used for the study. The researcher applied the simple random sampling technique in achieving this. The researcher visited the Yakurr Forestry charge office to obtain the list of forest communities. The names of the communities were written on pieces of paper and folded into ball-like shapes, which were poured into a container. The researcher mixed them properly and blindly selected six paper balls from the container with replacement. To select the respondents used for the study, the systematic random sampling technique was adopted. In each of the communities selected for the study, the researcher numbered the houses in the community. Every tenth house was selected for the study. In each house selected, one respondent was picked. These respondents across the various forest communities formed the sample for the study. The sample for this study consisted of three hundred (300) respondents randomly selected from five (5) forest communities in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The sample distribution is presented in Table 1.

The instrument considered most appropriate for data collection was a questionnaire and it was tagged Traditional Belief and Forest Resource Conservation Questionnaire (TBFRCQ). It consists of two parts, part A contains items on respondent demographic data while B was designed using four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) & Strongly Disagree (SD).

Table 1: Sample distribution table

S/N Names of communities	Pop of unit	Percentage	Samples
Ugep	1180	5%	59
Adim	1220	5%	61
Mkpani	1330	5%	67

Ekori	1100	5%	55
Asiga	1150	5%	58
Total	5980		300

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Items 1-5 measured traditional belief; Items 6-15 measured the dependent variable forest resource conservation. The researcher presented the designed questionnaire to experts in research and statistics for screening and finally to the supervisor for face and content validity. Through this process, modification and corrections were made to some of the items in the instrument. The corrections were effected before a trial copy was produced for data collection. Data used for the study was obtained directly from respondents through the use of questionnaire designed for data collection. The researcher with the aid of a trained research assistant visited all the communities selected for the study to administer the questionnaire. In each of the selected communities, permission of the village heads was obtained before the administration of the questionnaire. Total of three hundred (300) questionnaires were administered and retrieved in few days in order to allow the respondents respond properly to the questionnaire as well as enable the researcher to retrieve all the administered instruments. The data obtained in the study was coded by assigning numerical scores to each response in the questionnaire for positively worded items, strongly agree (SA) was scored 4. Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1.

Presentation of Results and Discussion

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation.

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State

Variables	X	SD	Cal-r	P.value
Traditional belief	15.534	2.4265	.364*	.000
Forest resources conservation	30.132	3.5876		

*Significant at.05; df=294;

The independent variable in this hypothesis is traditional belief while the dependent variable is forest resources conservation. Pearson product moment correlation statistical tool was used for data analysis. The result of this analysis is presented in Table 2. The result of analysis of data presented in Table 2 shows that the calculated r-value of .364 is higher than the p.value of .000 at.05 level of significance with 294 degree of freedom. The implication of this result is that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Discussion of findings

The finding obtained from analysis of data and testing hypothesis in the study revealed that the null hypothesis was rejected; the implication of this finding is that there was a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The reason for this finding could be that mixed cropping is often considered as an environment-friendly conservation practice. The practice of traditional beliefs promotes soil conservation and by extension forest conservation. This finding is in agreement with that of Tiwari (2018) that the role of traditional beliefs in the protection of natural resources is reflected in a variety of practices including sacred groves and sacred landscapes for example, in India, particular patches of forest are designated as sacred groves under customary law and are protected from any product extraction by the community. Such forests are very rich in biological diversity and harbour many endangered plant species including rare herbs and medicinal plants.

The finding of this study also supported that of Shastri, (2012). The gods or goddess communicate its will to the people through the juju priest or chief priest. The belief system is that the gods protect the community members from harm, famine, impotent, drought, epidemics and war among others. The gods avenge their anger on whoever omits or commits any flaw for which their presence forbids; hence, the cultural system holds to a very high esteem all the precepts of the laws of the gods.

Conclusion

The results obtained from data analysis testing in the study revealed the following: there is a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in the study area. Based on the finding it was then concluded that there is a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained in the study, the researcher made the following recommendations;

1. Agricultural extension workers and Environmental Educators should continue to encourage farmer to engage in conservation method in order to promote forest resources conservation
2. Farmers should be adequately and regularly sensitized on the need to participate in committee conservation club, which would reduce the dangers posed by bush burning, deforestation and promote forest resources conservation
3. Self-initiative as a practice should be discouraged among farmers in the study area in order to promote forest conservation and sustainable forest management.
4. Agricultural extension workers should ensure that members of forest communities are adequately sensitized on the need to effectively participate forest conservation practice to promote a healthy environment.

Acknowledgements

The researchers immensely appreciate the contributions of other authors/researchers whose studies enabled the successful completion of this research work. The contribution of the residents of communities sampled will always stand out and we appreciate all the participants. Finally, we appreciate the experts whose expertise were consulted for the best outcome of this article.

References

- Appiah-Opoku S (2017). *Indigenous beliefs and environmental stewardship: a rural Ghana experience*. *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor*. 7(3):15-17.
- Eneji, C.V.O., Gubo, Q., Jian, X., Oden, S.N., & Okpiliya, F.I. (2009). A Review of the Dynamics of Forest Resources Valuation and Community Livelihood: Issues, Arguments and concerns. *Journal of Agriculture biotechnology and ecology, China*. 2(2):210-231.
- FAO. (2015). *Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015: How are the World's Forests Changing?* Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
- Henshey, L. (2011). *Religious & Spiritual Mysteries Examiner*.
- Lori, A. C. (2019). Shifting Public Values for Forest Management: Making Sense of Wicked Problems. *Western Journal of Applied Forestry*, 14(1):28-34.
- National Population Commission (2023). *The 2023 population projection*.
- Olujobi O. J. (2015). Evaluation of the contributions of Ikere Forest Reserve to sustainable livelihood of adjoining communities in Ekiti State. *Journal of Research in Forestry, Wildlife and Environment*, 7(2)
- Sam, I.E. & Usang, N.O. (2018). Influence of African traditional religion and practices on sustainable conservation of natural resources in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. *World Development*, 29,1115-1136
- Shastri C.M, Bhat D.M, Nagaraja B.C, Murali, K. S, Ravindranath N.H. (2012). Tree species diversity in a village ecosystem in Uttara Kannada district in Western Ghats, Karnataka. *Curr. Sci.* 82:1080-1084
- Tiwari B.K, (2018). Biodiversity value, status, and strategies for conservation of sacred groves of Meghalaya, India. *Ecosystem. Health* 4:20-32.